

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Ligands at Different Ionic Strengths

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The dissociation constants of salicylic acid, 5-sulphosalicylic acid, 2,2'-dipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline and 5-nitro-1, 10-phenanthroline have been determined in presence of KCl of varying ionic-strengths to explore the role of neutral electrolytes.

LITTLE is known regarding the effects of 'neutral electrolytes' on the dissociation constants of ligands and their complexes in view of lack of systematic attempts to explore it. The determination of the thermodynamic dissociation constants are difficult due to extremely limited or no knowledge of the activities of different constituents of the system e.g.,

Thermodynamic dissociation constants are generally obtained by

- 1) Determining the dissociation constants at infinitely dilute solutions where feasible¹.
- 2) Determining the dissociation constants at different ionic strengths and using various extrapolations²⁻⁸.
- 3) Determining the dissociation constant at any particular ionic strength and making activity corrections using different theoretical as well as semiempirical equations which are valid at best upto 0.1 M²⁻⁸.

But the exact thermodynamic dissociation constants are more or less elusive. Thus, most of the workers⁴⁻⁸ prefer to use a constant "ionic medium" so that the formation constant at any particular ionic strength may be calculated. Unfortunately, the effect of different electrolytes (having the same ionic strength) on the dissociation constants are different and the comparisons of the results are also difficult unless the determinations are carried out at the same ionic strength using the same electrolytes.

Furthermore, the increased knowledge of the ion-solvent interactions have pointed to a number of limitations particularly when the ionic strengths are high. These are:

- 1) In presence of electrolytes, the solvent molecules would be highly polarised and variation of dielectric constant from 1.78 near the ions to bulk dielectric constant 78.5 would occur^{9,10}. A variation of

static dielectric constant of the solvent e.g., D=71.0 in presence of 0.5 M LiCl to D=51.0 at 2.0 M LiCl at 25°¹¹ in presence of electrolytes is also observed.

- 2) The activity coefficients of uncharged electrolyte are altered to different extents in presence of different electrolytes i.e (a) CH₃COOH=1.16 in 1m NaCl and 0.97 in 1m CH₃COONa¹².
- 3) There is a breakdown of the tetrahedral water structure in presence of ions¹³ and ions are solvated resulting in a decrease in the effective concentration of solvent molecule particularly when the electrolyte concentration is high¹³⁻¹⁴. Solvation of different ions are different¹⁵.
- 4) Ion-association leads to the reduction of ionic-strength and association between the ions of neutral electrolyte with reacting species also lead to a number of complications.

It is thus desirable to determine the dissociation constants of ligands at different ionic strengths using different electrolytes and analyse the results in the light of observations above and explore the various factors affecting the dissociation constants of the ligands.

In order to explore the role of "neutral electrolytes" on the dissociation constants of ligands, we determined the dissociation constants of ligands of different charge types

B=1, 10-phenanthroline or
5-nitro-1, 10-phenanthroline,
2, 2'-dipyridyl.

HA \rightleftharpoons H⁺+A⁻ HA=Salicylic acid.

HA⁻ \rightleftharpoons H⁺+A⁻ HA⁻=5-sulpho-salicylic acid.

in presence of "neutral electrolyte" KCl at different ionic strengths (0.03, 0.05, 0.08, 0.10, 0.20, 0.50, 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 M respectively). The results are described in the present communication.

Experimental

1, 10-Phenanthroline, 2, 2'-dipyridyl, salicylic acid, 5-sulphosalicylic acid, hydrochloric acid, caustic soda, potassium chloride, acetic acid and other reagents were of G. R. (B. M.) grade. 5-Nitro-1, 10-phenanthroline (B.D.H) was used. The acids were estimated in the usual way. The solutions were prepared by dissolving the weighed quantity of the acid. In the measurement of *pK* values above 4.0, sodium-acetate-acetic acid buffers were used whereas for measurements of *pK* values below 4, HCl acid was used. KCl solutions were used to keep the ionic strength to the desired value. The solutions were made from double-distilled water.

All the ligands absorb strongly in the u.v. region and the experimental details are the same as given in earlier communications¹.

For the determination of *pK* values, the o.d readings of the ligands in excess acid (N/10 HCl or more as the case may be) and in nearly neutral (in case of salicylic acid, sulphosalicylic acid) or in excess alkali (N/10 NaOH solutions) and at intermediate *pH*s were taken at the analytical wave lengths. These are :

- a) 310 nm and 315 nm for salicylic acid and 5-sulphosalicylic acid.
- b) 300 nm and 305 nm for 2, 2'-dipyridyl.
- c) 255 nm and 260 nm for 1, 10-phenanthroline.
- d) 280 nm for 5-nitro 1, 10-phenanthroline.

The blank solutions were of the same composition as in the experimental solutions except the ligand.

Spectrophotometric readings were taken with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer. *pH* measurements were made with a Cambridge Bench type battery operated *pH*-meter. All measurements were done at 25°.

Results

At any particular ionic strength, the values for the reactions (1), (2) and (3) can be represented as

$$pK = pH + \log \frac{[BH^+]}{[B]} \text{ or } pH + \log \frac{[HA]}{[A]} \quad \dots (3)$$

(with appropriate charges)

The expression is ultimately written as

$$pK = pH \pm \log \frac{d - d_M}{d_i - d} \quad \dots (4)$$

as the case may be, where

d_M = o.d of the molecular form

d_i = o.d of the ionic form

d = o.d at any intermediate *pH* at the wavelengths of measurement.

Thus, from the values of *pH*, *d_M*, *d_i* and *d*, *pK* values can be calculated. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Temp. 25°	<i>pK</i> -values				
Ionic strength	Salicylic acid	Sulpho-salicylic acid	2,2'-Dipyridyl	1,10-Phenanthroline	5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline
0.03	2.97	2.78	4.61	5.11	3.29
0.05	2.96	2.74	4.63	5.15	3.29
0.08	2.94	2.63	4.63	5.13	3.30
0.10	2.93	2.48	4.75	5.12	3.36
0.20	2.91	2.46	4.75	5.23	3.55
0.50	2.76	2.29	4.82	5.23	3.59
1.00	3.14	2.10	5.32	5.30	3.72
2.00	2.94	2.11	5.45	5.39	3.43
3.00	2.62	2.13	5.61	5.49	3.70

It is to be noted in this connection that *pH* refers to activity of hydrogen ion concentration and $\frac{d - d_M}{d_i - d}$ refers to the ratio of the concentration of $\frac{[HA]}{[A]}$ or $\frac{[BH^+]}{[B]}$.

Discussion

In view of the absence of systematic studies of the effect of ions on the dissociation constants of ligands and complexes, it is very difficult to visualize the exact picture. The *pK* values at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (with KCl, KNO₃, NaNO₃) range from 4.33-4.51 for 2, 2'-dipyridyl; 4.8-5.2 for 1, 10-phenanthroline; 2.82-3.00 for salicylic acid (3.70 at $\mu = 0.2 M$ and 3.86 at 3 *M* NaClO₄); 2.27-2.49 for sulphosalicylic acid (2.67 at 3*M* NaClO₄ and 2.33 in 1.0 *M* KNO₃).

The thermodynamic *pK_T* values are :-

1, 10-phenanthroline = 4.96 - 5.05^{1,2*}

2, 2'-dipyridyl = 4.47 - 4.51^{1,2*}

5-NO₂-1, 10- = 3.23^{1,2*}, 3.33 (at $\mu = 0.10$)²¹ phenanthroline

Salicylic acid = 2.97^{1,2*}, 3.04²²

5-Sulphosalicylic acid = 2.74^{16,22}
(Dissociation of the carboxyl group)

From the results given in Tables 1, it is observed that pK values (though not strictly concentration quotient as pH measures the activity of hydrogen ion) salicylic and 5-sulphosalicylic acid generally decrease as the ionic strength increases, the reverse trend is observed in case of 2, 2'-dipyridyl, 1, 10-phenanthroline and 5-nitro-1, 10-phenanthroline. It is expected as the thermodynamic values are obtained by the addition of contributions due to activity coefficients of anions or cations to pK values which is positive in the former case and negative in case of the latter.

In case of 'isoelectronic reactions', it is expected that 'ionic strength' should not change the pK values to a considerable extent. It has been actually found that the pK -values are more or less unchanged at low ionic strengths (upto about 0.1 M), but when the ionic strengths are high, a considerable change in the pK -values is observed. It is to be noted in this connection that pK values change by about 0.5 pK units in case of 1, 10-phenanthroline and 5-nitro-1, 10-phenanthroline but the change is about 1.0 pK units in case of 2, 2'-dipyridyl. It is known that both Ph and Dipy have the same type of linkages, there is difference in pK values obviously due to 'resonance stabilization' and fixed coplanarity in case of Ph compared to Dipy, where there is free-rotation. The greater change of pK -values of Dipy at higher ionic strengths might be due to the presence of highly structured solvent environment and considerable 'electrostriction'. The number of free water molecules or free-space become unavailable leading to the restriction of free rotation which ultimately increases the pK -values due to coplanarity.

It is to be noted that the dissociation constants as presented in the table are not true concentration quotients as the pH s of the solutions measured refer to the activities of H^+ ion. Furthermore, liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude which increases with increase in salt concentration limits the accuracy of the determination of the stability constants.

It is very difficult to say quantitatively the exact contributions of the different factors affecting the stability constants. It is likely that the different factors may have opposing effects on the dissociation constants.

However, to have some understanding regarding the role of 'neutral electrolytes' on the dissociation constants, it is necessary to have a detailed study regarding the effect of neutral electrolyte on the activity coefficient of the different ions, the extent of possible ion-pair formation, solvation etc as enumerated earlier. Moreover, detailed study of the effect of different 'neutral electrolytes' on the dissociation constants are to be undertaken.

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